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Law enforcement against rural wild dumps in Romania – Satu Mare County case study

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As a new EU Member, Romania faces serious challenges in providing reliable waste management services in rural areas and illegal waste disposal is still an issue.

The paper examines the closure effects of wild dumps in order to start a better waste management in rural areas.

In Satu Mare County urban areas, waste collection increased from 70% in 2007 to 100% in 2009. MSW is transported to two urban landfills of Tasnad and Satu Mare cities. With the support of EU funds, a regional sanitary landfill, 2 transfer stations (in Carei and Negresti-Oas cities), 4 micro-transfer stations (in Tasnad and Livada cities, Valea Vinului and Belciug communes) will be created. In rural areas, waste collection increased from 7% in 2007 up to 71% in 2009. But the lack of a regular waste collection service led to an uncontrolled waste disposal in local dumps. Most of rural municipalities had dumps in public areas until the EU adhesion. The closure and monitoring of these sites before July 2009 had obliged several Local Authorities to provide basic waste management services. These sites had to be closed and rehabilitated under a simplified procedure according to Minister Order nr. 1275/2005.

The conventional landfills had to be closed according to the Government Decision nr. 345/2005 (which transposes the EU Landfill Directive 1999/31) following the technical normative Order 757/2004. 122 dumps were compacted and soil covered. No dump was moved or transported to urban landfills (CCSM, 2010).

Wild dumps remain a current environmental threat in rural Romania and in small urban areas, and the plain region of Satu Mare County favours waste accumulation in large dumps. The total dumping volume registered is 355,340 m³ equivalent to 142,136 tons of waste disposed using a specific density of 400 kg/m³. The demographic features and spatial patterns of human settlements influence the uncollected generated waste disposal method.

Reference

CCSM (County Council of Satu Mare), 2010. County Waste Management Plan. Monitoring Report 2009.